

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

FLAGSHIP PROJECT GRIP

SPOKE 2 –GREEN TECHNOLOGIES AND SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIES

DELIVERABLE D2.4.2 “New characterized material from biomasses”

REPORTING PERIOD	
Period covered:	from M8 to M 28
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Deliverable # Responsible	Boccaleri-Laurenti-Binda
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List of Deliverables

D. No	Name	Type	Disseminati on Level	Due Date	Delivery Date (actual)
[number]	[name]	[R — Document, report] [DEM — Demonstrator, pilot, prototype] [DEC — Websites, patent filings, videos, etc] [DATA — data sets, microdata, etc] [DMP — Data Management Plan] [ETHICS] [SECURITY] [OTHER]	[PU — Public] [SEN — Sensitive] [R] [C] [S]	[month number]	[dd/mm/yyyy]
D2.1	Data about chemical and nutritional profiling of raw wastes and by products	R	PU	M14	18/04/2024
D2.2.1	On line lab-scale technical multi-device for waste processing*	Other (material)	PU	M18	25/10/2024
D2.2.2	Delivery of protocols (lab-scale) ready to scale-up the production of new high-value material (in collaboration with Companies)	R	PU	M22	16/02/2025
D2.3.1	New data about valorized matrices characterization and high value products	R	PU	M28	30/09/2025
D2.3.2	New characterized ingredients/materials for food, nutraceuticals, pharma and cosmetic applications	Other (material)	PU	M30	30/09/2025
D2.4.1	New data about sustainable production of new materials from biomasses	R	PU	M24	
D2.4.2	New characterized materials from biomasses	Other (material)	PU	M30	30/09/2025
D2.5.2	Porous sorbents from biomasses valorization	Other (material)	PU	M30	29/09/2025
D2.6.1	New material produced at pilot scale ready to the formulation or co-formulation (in collaboration with Companies)	Other (material)	PU	M32	
D2.6.2	New well characterized process and formulated pilot-products (in collaboration with Companies)	R/Other (Material)	PU	M32	

D2.7	Report on the adsorption and/or catalytic performances of porous solids derived from biomasses valorization and non-recyclable plastic wastes	R	PU	M32	29/09/2025
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A) INTRODUCTION

The work and the outcomes reported in this Deliverable are related to the activity scheduled in Task 2.2 (focusing on Sub-Task 2.2.3 and Sub-Task 2.2.4). The main goal was the preparation and the characterization of the plant/recalcitrant biomasses useful to produce new material ready to be used in cement/biopolymers/polymer composite production/fine chemicals, as well as new high-value chemicals (biosurfactants).

B) ROLE OF PARTNERS

The role of the Partners involved in this activity (Disit-UPO, UNIPV, UNITO) was to apply the best performing methods to up-cycle the raw biomasses (from different origin, animal and plant-derived materials), in order to obtain their complete characterization, as well as some data about the high-value molecules/materials recovered.

C) EXPLANATION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT AND OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRESS

Following we report the characterization of the main materials from biomasses (rice husk; soy; cow milk whey and *Elodea nuttalii*, used cooked oil).

The characterization of further matrices (e.g. cocoa bean husks) were provided in other Deliverables.

Disit-UPO

Rice husk has been characterized to understand the intrinsic features and design the treatment optimization. Particular care was devoted to the evaluation of the inorganic content, as the high silica amount of the dried rice husk basically limits its conversion. Such amount, despite related to the type of rice and its geographical origin, determined after calcination, is about 20% wt. of which about 85% is composed by amorphous silica. Rice husk was provided an industrial sample provided by a rice production plant sited in Morano Po (VC).

Its characterization required XRPD, TGA, XRF and SS-NMR; this characterization protocol allowed to understand its composition and validate the most efficient strategy for chemicals and materials recovery. Rice husk was calcined to obtain the inorganic

fraction, on which the elemental composition was evaluated by XRF using the glass disk obtained after borate flux fusion method. The elements, reported as oxides, and the relative percentages in weight are reported in the table.

The composition is typical of a natural-based matrix, i.e. the presence of the soil elements (K, P, Mn, Mg..).

Oxide	Weight Percentage
SiO ₂	85,64
K ₂ O	4,14
CaO	4,05
SO ₃	1,40
P ₂ O ₅	1,02
Fe ₂ O ₃	0,96
Cl	0,84
Al ₂ O ₃	0,74
MnO	0,59
MgO	0,37
Na ₂ O	0,08
TiO ₂	0,06

Table 1: Elemental composition by XFR on calcined Rice husk

The XRPD of the residue of the inorganic fraction (Figure 1 – right) highlights the presence of cristobalite phase (a polymorph of quartz) resulting from the densification of the silica fraction during the thermal treatment.

Fig. 1

On the contrary, the XRPD pattern of rice husk (Figure 1 XRPD - left) does not show signals related to Si oxides or in general to its inorganic content, while several broad peaks and some sharp signals are due to the presence of cellulose, characterized by a crystalline structure. The amorphous halos of hemicellulose, lignin and silica can be seen at the lower angles. The inserts in the XRPD figure are the images of rice husk, raw and after calcination.

Figure 2: ^{29}Si and ^{13}C -MAS-NMR spectra

Based on the high silica content, the ^{29}Si SS-NMR was collected to define the silicon coordination (see figure NMR top). Silicon is in high polymerization state because,

according to the chemical shift, Q^3 (3 bonds Si-O-Si and 1 OH) and Q^4 (all Si-O-Si bonds) coordination's are observed. The organic fraction was analysed by ^{13}C SS-NMR and the spectrum is in figure - bottom. Peaks from the main components of rice husk can be observed at 63, 73, 83, 88 and 105 ppm for cellulose, at 21 and 171 ppm associated with acetate groups of hemicellulose (besides peaks in coincidence with cellulose), and at 56 and between 116 and 152 ppm (aromatic carbons) for lignin.

Figure 3: TGA profile of rice husk and relative dTG recorded under airflow (RT- 900 °C – 10 °C/min)

The thermogravimetric profile recorded under air flow shows the presence of three main weight losses: first the dehydration and the other two are the combustion of lignin and cellulose. With the help of the dTG profile, a rough organic composition can be determined, because if the first weight loss is characterized by a low combustion rate, revealing that rice husk does not contain many volatile molecules. On the other hand, the high combustion rate of the second loss is ascribable to rice husk with low lignin content.

All these findings permitted the complete evaluation of the characteristics of the rice husk sample, ready for the preparation of derived material useful to be inserted in cement as additive.

CHEM-UniTO

Soybean hulls, another biomass considered in RM2 activity, have been characterized through different techniques to study their composition and chemical-physical properties. They showed a negatively charged surface with a measured point of zero charge a pH value close to 2. The elemental composition was also studied through the elemental analysis. The wt % average content of C, H, N, S was 41.37 ± 0.08 ; 6.09 ± 0.05 ; 1.50 ± 0.06 ; 0.00 respectively while the calculated C/H ratio was 6.79.

The outcomes of soybean hulls' compositional analysis performed through the NREL protocol are reported in Figure 5-left. The main components are hemicellulose (49%) and cellulose (42%) while lignin (4%) and the lipidic fraction (5%) are a minority. These components are organized in fibrils as shown in FESEM image (Figure 5-right).

Figure 4: -Composition (left) and FESEM image (right) of soybean hulls

Rice husks' ashes have been obtained from a *waste-to-energy* process of an important company located in Piedmont. Morphological analysis and microanalysis (Figure 6A

and 6B) showed an heterogeneous composition characterized by the predominance of C and Si atoms. The high Si content (22 g/100 g of ashes) was confirmed through the XRF analysis (Figure 6C) which also allowed to exclude the presence of dangerous heavy metals. Si is contained in the form of silica as evidenced by the ATR-FTIR spectra which showed the characteristic pattern of SiO₂ (Figure 6D).

Figure 5: Rice husk ashes characterization: A) FESEM-EDS microanalysis; B) FESEM images; C) XRF results; D) ATR-FTIR spectrum

UNITO (DBIOS)

Material collection, extraction and quantification of high value molecules from *Elodea nuttallii*

UNITO (DBIOS) carried out surveys to detect the presence of the alien aquatic plant *Elodea nuttallii* in the stretch of the River Po between Villafranca Piemonte and Casale Monferrato. Elodea was found from spring 2023 onwards at various locations along the stretch; its biomass increased significantly during the summer months and then decreased again towards autumn. This trend was confirmed over the following

two years. Biomass was assessed as dry weight per unit area and reached high maximum values of approximately 1 kg/m². Samples of *E. nuttallii* were collected, rinsed with water to remove epiphytic algae or other organisms from the plant surface, and stored at -18°C for subsequent biochemical analysis.

The algal biomass (Figure 6A) was defrosted and dried in an oven at 50 °C for 12 hours (Figure 6B). It was then mechanically crushed to increase their surface area (Figure 6C).

Figure 6. *Elodea nuttallii* biomass A) before and B) after drying, C) after mechanical treatment. D) Biomass extract

The dried plant biomass was subjected to alkaline treatment with a 4 M sodium hydroxide (NaOH) solution at 70 °C for 1 hour. A fixed ratio of plant dry weight to solvent volume of 1:10 (g/ml) was employed. The resulting extract (Figure 1D) was subsequently processed through liquid-liquid extraction using hexane as the organic solvent. The solvent was then evaporated to yield a final concentration equivalent to 100 mg of dry sample weight per milliliter of hexane.

The identification and quantification of the *Elodea* extract were performed by gas chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry (GC/MS). Four compounds were

quantified by reference to calibration curves obtained through the injection of known amounts of cholesterol, squalene, phytol, and β -sitosterol standards.

The quantification results are shown in the table 2.

Name	Concentration (μM)	$\mu\text{g/g}$ of dry weight (ppm)
Colesterol	33.7 ± 3.1	130 ± 12
Squalene	9.1 ± 1.7	37.5 ± 7.1
Fitol	2621 ± 23	7774.2 ± 70.3
β -Sitosterol	156.5 ± 2.9	649.2 ± 12.1

Tab. 2. Composition of Elodea extract (bioactive compounds).

UNIPV

Characterization of WP (whey permeate)

The concentration of lactose and the traces of galactose contained in WP were determined by using Lactose/D-Galactose Rapid Assay Kit (K-LACGAR) from Megazyme NEOGEN (Ireland) following supplier indications. Traces of D-glucose contained in WP were determined by using GOPOD kit from Megazyme NEOGEN (Ireland) following supplier indications. WP used as biomass (Figure 7) for the enzymatic biotransformations contained 45 g L^{-1} lactose with traces of glucose (0.09 g L^{-1}) and galactose (0.03 g L^{-1}). WP was not submitted to a further characterization as the information necessary for using this biomass as precursor of bio-based surfactants was the sugar content.

Figure 7. WP used as biomass for the enzymatic biotransformations

Characterization of rice huks

- Pre-treatment and characterization of RH (rice husk)

Rice husk from the Pavia area was dried at 40 °C and milled by a knife-mil for 5 min. Once ground, the powder was sieved and the 250-600 µm fraction was used. Rice husk was submitted to two different pretreatments to enrich it in cellulose/hemicellulose fraction by using either a conventional two-step chemical process (dewaxing with n-Hex:EtOH and delignification with NaOH) (CEF treatment 1) or an alternative treatment in the presence of the DES choline chloride:lactic acid 1:5 (CEF treatment 2). In Figure 8 the SEM analysis of milled RH, RH from CEF treatment 1 and CEF treatment 2 is reported. Both treatments allowed to obtain a (hemi)cellulose-enriched fraction (CEF) (yield: 50% w/w) as confirmed by TGA, DSC, (Figure 9), FTIR (Figure 10) and BET (Figure 11) analysis.

Figure 8. SEM analysis (Zeiss EVO MA10 Carl Zeiss, working distance 8.5 mm, beam voltage 10 kV, SE).

Figure 9. Thermogravimetric analysis (Q5000 TAINstrument, N₂ flux, 10 °C/min, 25 °C to 700 °C). Differential Scanning Calorimetry (Q2000 TAINstrument, N₂ flux, 10 °C/min; -20 °C to 350 °C and back). Red= without treatment, Green= treatment 1, Pink= treatment 2.

Figure 10. Attenuated Total Reflectance ATR-FTIR analysis (Nicolet iS20 Thermo Fisher Scientific; 4000 - 600 cm⁻¹, count step 4 cm⁻¹, diamond crystal).

Sample	BET (m ² /g)	Pore volume (cm ³ /g)
Husk	16.4±0.5	-
Treatment 1	8.84±0.3	-
Treatment 2	48.1±0.3	0.10

Figure 11. Porosimetry (3Flex analyzer Micromeritics; 77 K; after degas at 400 K, specific surface area determined by the BET method).

- Characterization of UCO (used cooking oil)

The lipid species present in UCO (Figure 12) were determined after its purification by flash chromatography (*n*-Hex/Et₂O, 80:20). UCO is mainly composed of triglycerides (76.4%), but it also contains a percentage equal to 23.6% of mono- and diglycerides (MAG/DAG) and free fatty acids (FFA) (Figure 13).

Figure 12. UCO used as biomass for the enzymatic biotransformations

Figure 13. Lipid species identified in UCO.

Fatty acid composition of UCO was determined by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) analysis after base-catalyzed transmethylation (Figure 14). Fatty acid composition of UCO is reported in Figure 15.

Figure 14. GC-MS chromatogram.

Figure 15. Fatty acid composition of UCO. PA= palmitic acid, SA= stearic acid, OA= oleic acid, LA= linoleic acid.